

Active learning in grey-box models for near-real-time on-line monitoring of dynamic processes

M. B. Dodt¹, A. Persoons¹, M. G. R. Faes^{1,2}, D. Moens¹

¹ KU Leuven, LMSD Division, Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Jan Pieter de Nayerlaan 5, 2860 Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium

² TU Dortmund, Chair for Reliability Engineering,
Leonhard-Euler-Strasse 5, 44227, Dortmund, Germany

Abstract

Near-real-time monitoring of dynamical processes in a production line can aid greatly in increasing the products quality and reliability, leading to an overall extended lifetime and reduced costs. It enables timely intervention in case of diminishing quality or necessary parameter adjustment. In order to do so automatically, a model that can continuously update and evaluate itself and its future predictions with high reliability is of utmost importance. A so-called digital twin is well suited to perform this task, as its digital model is able to update and estimate the future development as well as compute necessary countermeasures. The digital twin is here modelled as a grey-box, which unites the high-accuracy of the white-box, numerical physical model (i.e. FE model) with the computation speed of a black-box data-based Kriging surrogate model. A key feature of the proposed approach is active refinement of the black-box model in parallel to performing process control. The former is an adaptive calibration scheme, considering process drift as well as accuracy of the surrogate.

1 Introduction

Numerical simulation tools have been used for multiple decades for product design and optimisation thereof. In recent years, the interest increased to study the manufacturing process in more depth through first-principle based models in order to gain more knowledge on the effect process parameters have on the product quality. While this is usually performed in an off-line setting on the general interrelations, the ability to communicate with sensors and actuators in real time are revolutionising the potential of simulations and shifting the area of implementation onto the on-line setting.

It is essential in a well-performing on-line setting to consider and propagate the process uncertainties. Propagating uncertainties in time-dependent processes is no trivial, but nevertheless crucial task, even more so, for instationary processes. This prevents us to make accurate long term predictions. Instationarity in manufacturing processes is for example caused by process drift, which is often times unpredictable and can cause significant production defects if not accounted for. A way to alleviate this problem is to regularly measure the behavior of the system, re-calibrating the model predictions using model updating techniques, which is the main focus of structural health monitoring. Of course the frequency of the measurement related to the time-scales involved in the prediction can have a great influence on the efficiency of the approach. For some fast processes it becomes necessary to have a constant measurement feedback from the process. The recent developments on computation tools and sensor rendered this types of implementation increasingly common in the industry and initiated the idea of so-called digital twins.

The idea behind a digital twin is to couple real-time measurements with numerical simulation models to create a model that is perpetually adjusting its calibration to fit the behavior of the system. Such a model could allow us to make real-time predictions and have control over the process which would be very promising for a wide range of applications such as simulation, production optimization or process control. The first imple-

mentation of digital twins dates over 10 years ago [1], however recent years have seen a change in ability and the digital twin is becoming more and more crucial to attain the Industry 4.0 standard [2][3]. While its application was initially heavily focused on the macroscopic aspects of monitoring and on the global system itself for predictive control and pro-active maintenance [4][5], there is a recent shift towards the more detail-oriented aspects of manufacturing that is rapidly evolving. Literature on general applications is scarce however, so far it is only available on very specific manufacturing processes such as metal injection moulding [6], additive manufacturing [7][8] and recently on production quality control [9]. That is because such an approach poses great challenges, the first one being the computation time. This limitation comes from the computation burden of evaluating the digital twin model. The physical phenomenon modelled are often very complex or multi-physics and may induce computation times incompatible with “real-time” simulations. This issue is particularly troublesome for phenomenon that are both complex to model and physically fast to perform such as in-line manufacturing operations. Under those conditions there is no hope of predicting the behavior of the process before it physically occurs, limiting the use of the digital twin.

The second main source of complexity are the multiple sources of uncertainties limiting the accuracy of the predictions. Uncertainties are usually considered following two type, the epistemic (due to a lack of knowledge) and aleatory uncertainties (irreducible, inherent variability of the phenomenon). In a digital-twin implementation both types are expected to affect sensors data, assumed behavior or even model parameters. Uncertainty quantification methods are dedicated to the propagation of such uncertainties to estimated their influence on the prediction. However, these methods usually rely on computationally intensive probabilistic analysis further increasing the computation time issues.

An approach know as surrogate-modelling has gained increasing attention in the past few decades for its potential in decreasing the computation burden of uncertainty quantification analysis. The idea behind it is to calibrate a mathematical object to emulate the behavior of the model without simulating the physics. The evaluation of the surrogate is extremely fast and complex probabilistic analysis can be easily performed with it, however, it introduces an addition modeling error related to the quality of its calibration. Kriging [10][11][12][13] is a kind of surrogate model that has become very popular mostly thanks to its ability to estimate its own localized accuracy. This property allowed the development of adaptive-Kriging approaches aiming at iteratively refining the calibration of the surrogate in a near-optimal way. This approach falls into the category of so-called grey-box approaches aiming at efficiently combining physics-based white-box models with data-based black-box ones.

Using this framework there is a potential for building a very efficient grey-box digital-twin where the calibration of both the physical model and the surrogate are perpetually refined. This paper presents a scheme for such a coupling particularly focused on the process monitoring of resistance spot welding production lines. The scheme is illustrated on a simplified toy problem only considering two parameters: controllable process parameters and non-controllable variables affected by process drift. The latter can only be known within the bounds of an interval representing the uncertainty related to process drift. A Kriging surrogate model is calibrated to mimic the performances of the physical model. Using the surrogate prediction a worst-case process reliability is estimated which in turn guides the decision regarding how the process should proceed between continuing, adjusting the controllable parameter or stopping and awaiting operator action.

The objective of this paper is to introduce a scheme combining white-box and black-box models into a grey-box model, making use of their respective benefits to perform near-real-time process control on a dynamic, non-linear problem. An adaptive calibration scheme is developed that is taking into account process drift and the accuracy of the black-box model, avoiding to operate in areas of low surrogate accuracy and refining itself adaptively if necessary.

At first resistance spot welding is introduced in chapter 2 and the digital twin is discussed in more detail. In chapter 3, the proposed methodology is discussed and the workflow presented. Following that the methodology is applied in chapter 4 and finally the paper is concluded in chapter 5.

Figure 1: Cross section of the formation of a welding nugget. Two electrodes are pressing the metal sheets together. The molten material forms the welding nugget.

2 Digital Twins for Resistance spot welding

As mentioned in the introduction, this work is focused on monitoring on-line resistance spot-welding (RSW). It is a manufacturing technique used in almost all industries, and is, especially in the car and battery manufacturing, of great importance. Here two thin metal sheets are joined at a localised spot, giving the method its name. A modern vehicle consists of 2000 to 5000 individual spot welds with a good car production line producing more than 7 million welds a day [14]. At the spot where the junction is formed, two metal sheets are pressed together by electrodes. Current is sent through the electrodes and consequently through the metal sheets. Because of the high resistance between the sheets, heat is generated which melts the metal at the specific spot, and joins them, forming the welding nugget. Figure 1 shows a cross-section of the nugget formation during welding.

Its popularity is mainly due to how easily RSW can be automated but the physics of the process are difficult to simulate, involving a complex thermo-electro-mechanical coupling as well as fluid flow and phase-change [14]. Multiple sources of uncertainties, strong non-linearities as well as a complex time-dependency further complicate the simulation. A schematic of a welding model can be seen in figure 2, with the force on the electrodes, the welding current and the total welding duration as input parameters and the weld properties, most significantly the nugget diameter as outputs. The latter's importance stems from the fact, that the yield strength of the weld is directly proportional to the nugget size, so a minimum diameter needs to be reached in order to have a successful weld. There is also an upper limit of the nugget size, as too much molten material, or pressing the electrodes onto the metal sheets with too much force can cause material defects such as expulsion. The amount of molten material can be influenced by the current sent through the electrodes and the total welding time. Over time, the welding process is influenced by a process drift caused by accumulation of dust and the wear and tear of the electrodes. The process drift shows itself as an uncontrolled and difficult to predict variation of the model parameters in time.

The quality of the welds are usually tested with destructive tests. Those are expensive and allow assessment only for a small sample size, which reduces their informative value. However, external and internal monitoring devices are available, enabling on-line process control [14].

Performing process control with a so-called digital twin allows for a near-real-time non-destructive weld quality estimation as well as process drift detection and active control, ensuring the optimal weld quality. Through that it is possible to improve the overall performance, increase production quality and reliability as well as reduce waste. A digital twin is a virtual representation of a physical process and can be seen as an extension on numerical models as it allows not only forward but also backward communication with the model and the process [5]. Because of that, it is possible to monitor the process almost real-time and by enhancing it to perform model updating and forecasting, the outcome can be predicted and guided to avoid failure. An-

Figure 2: Schematic representation of a welding model

other important feature of digital twins is that they are able to correct themselves unsupervised [15], which enables automation and can have a positive impact on the quality control as well as increasing the range of possible applications.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of RSW involving a digital twin.

Figure 3 illustrates how a digital twin is involved in the welding process. The process is observed by external sensors and used as an input to the digital twin. The digital twin updates itself and the process state and estimates the optimal input parameter for the next processes. These optimised parameters are then used as process parameters for the next welds. The digital twin is also able to estimate a reliability metric related to the probability of failure, in this case, of an insufficient weld quality. The uncertainties of the process are pointed out as well. They are among other found in the discrepancy of the input parameter and the actual process parameter or in the noisy observations.

In order to perform process control reliably, there are some challenges to overcome. As it became clear, welding is a very complex, highly non-linear process and as such a good welding model has a simulation time (~ 2 h) that is significantly higher than the actual process time (~ 70 ms). Furthermore, the process drift is uncontrolled, which makes the prediction of the variation of the model parameter in time difficult. Lastly, there are many different sources of uncertainty that need to be considered.

The uncertainties transform the problem at hand into a uncertainty quantification (UQ) problem, which are approached by a reliability analysis. The most common methods are based on random sampling approaches. However, to be able to have a statistical relevant assertion of the problem, a large number of samples need to be generated from the FE model, which quickly becomes computationally prohibitive. This FE model is sometimes also called white-box model as it gives physics-informed and transparent computation results. An alternative approach to avoid this problem is called surrogate or meta modelling, also dubbed as black-box modelling. The idea behind is to create an analytical model, that is very fast to evaluate and that was calibrated on physics-based data, such as measuring results or FE results. As it is an approximation of reality, the result quality depends strongly on how well the surrogate model is trained. The goal is therefore to find a good compromise between the modelling error and number of evaluated samples, in other words, the computational cost. One method to build a surrogate is the Kriging meta modelling, which is based on Gaussian processes [10][12]. Further details regarding this method are provided in the next section.

It is clear that process control cannot be performed by only relying on a physically informed white-box model i.e. a FE model, which is accurate but too slow. At the same time it cannot be performed solely based on data by relying on a black-box surrogate model, as it is fast but the accuracy varies and an additional error is introduced. Therefore, a grey-box digital twin is developed that utilises the advantages of both models. As a first step, an adaptive calibration scheme for the surrogate model is developed for a simplified example, that still contains all key elements. The model is actively refined while considering process drift and avoiding the operation in areas of low surrogate accuracy. That way, the digital twin is able to adapt the input parameters if necessary and at the same time refine itself, thus leading to more reliable and higher quality results.

3 Methodology

In the beginning of this chapter the general problem setting is introduced, followed by the digital twin's task in the context of monitoring and control. After a short discussion about Kriging meta modelling, a methodology that is able to perform progress control while considering uncertainties is presented in detail.

3.1 General setting

The outcome of a process such as RSW is largely influenced by two types of parameters. One is the operator-decided input parameter, which is controllable and in the following referred to as x_c . In RSW the controllable parameter are e.g. the electrode force, the current or the welding duration. The second type is the uncontrollable state parameter x_{uc} , which is affected by the unknown process drift, e.g. the resistance of the electrode. It is assumed that a physical model of the process exists, allowing us the definition of a performance function g linking the inputs to a measure of its performance y . In the context of RSW the performance can be linked to the nuggets size, which, as mention in section 2 can lead to a failure if it is too small or too big. This performance function is then defined in such a way that a negative value indicates a process failure. The relationship between the different parameters is displayed on the left hand side of figure 4. It can be seen, that each of these parameters is time dependent. As a simplification, the time is assumed to be discrete and one time step spans one process. The process duration and change of a parameter within one process is therefore not taken into account. In order to deal with the discrepancy between process and simulation time, and to keep the actual implementation to RSW in mind, process control is performed for multiple processes at once.

3.2 Model of the process drift

In order to make predictions for a proactive process-control an estimation of $x_{uc}^{t+\Delta t}$ is necessary. This quantity is affected by unpredictable process drift and is therefore inherently uncertain. It is possible to measure past instances of x_{uc}^t , however, its evolution in time is unknown. While there are many possible ways to model such an uncertainty, an exhaustive discussion about these models and inferences techniques is outside of the

Figure 4: Schematic overview over the proposed approach.

scope of this paper. It is instead proposed to take the simplifying yet quite general assumption that x_{uc}^t is a realisation of a Gaussian process over time. Therefore, knowing past values of x_{uc} , it is possible to calibrate a fitting Gaussian process using regression techniques [16]. Using the calibrated process, it becomes possible to make a stochastic prediction about the future values of x_{uc} . More precisely, each forecasted value \hat{x}_{uc}^{t+} is associated with a Gaussian distribution defined by a mean $\hat{\mu}_M(t)$ and a standard deviation $\hat{\sigma}_M(t)$. It was chosen to avoid assuming a distribution for the value of x_{uc}^{t+} and simply considered that it belongs to the confidence interval $I[\hat{x}_{uc}^{t+}] = \hat{\mu}_M(t) \pm \hat{\sigma}_M(t)$. In the context of this work, the Gaussian process is considered following a Matern 5/2 kernel, an illustration of a calibrated Gaussian process is given in figure 5. The grey area corresponds to the past values of x_{uc} available through measurement and used for the calibration of the process. The black lines corresponds to the process mean and bounds of the interval and the blue line represents the actual, unknown, evolution. This approach can be extended to the interval prediction of x_{uc} over the next n time steps by simply considering the minimum and the maximum bounds over the set of intervals $\{I[\hat{x}_{uc}^{t+\Delta t}], \dots, I[\hat{x}_{uc}^{t+n \cdot \Delta t}]\}$.

Figure 5: Estimating the next instances of x_{uc} with Gaussian Process Regression with a Matern 5/2 kernel function; shown for $t_i = 20$. The grey area shows the past values of x_{uc} that are considered in the GPR.

In order to keep the process quality in an acceptable range, the process drift needs to be accounted for. Figure 4 shows on the right hand side of the overview, how that is performed. The boundaries of the evolution of \hat{x}_{uc}^{t+} , estimated as described above, are used as input parameters for an optimisation loop. The digital twin predicts $\hat{g}(t)$ dependent on x_c for this interval and optimises x_c^{t+} so that the reliability of the system is maximised. This $x_{c,opt}^{t+}$ is then used as an input parameter for the next n processes.

3.3 Kriging meta modelling

As mentioned in the introduction it is proposed in this work to use the surrogate approach to mitigate the computation burden of evaluating a complex physical model. The principle is to calibrate a mathematical surrogate based on a set of calibration samples called a design of experiment (DoE). Once calibrated, the surrogate can be used in place of the numerical model while requiring a very limited computation burden. However there are two limitations of this approach, first the samples of the DoE need to be evaluated through the physical model, which could be computationally intensive. Second using a surrogate induces an extra modelling error related to the quality of the calibration.

It is proposed to use a Gaussian process for the architecture of the surrogate, also known as a Kriging model. Kriging was initially introduced in the context of global optimisation [11] and was further popularized in the context of adaptive Kriging Monte Carlo Simulation (AK-MCS) [12]. A more detailed overview is provided by Moustapha et al. [13], as it would be outside of the scope of this paper. The principle is very similar to how Gaussian process is detailed in section 3.2. The Kriging model will be calibrated to emulate the performance function of the process y . For each input vector $X = (x_{uc}, x_c)$ the Kriging model will associate a Gaussian random variable defined by its mean $\hat{\mu}_K(X)$ and standard deviation (STD) $\hat{\sigma}_K(X)$. The mean will then be considered as the Kriging estimated performance $\hat{y}(X) = \hat{\mu}_K(x)$ and the standard deviation can be used as an indicator of the imprecision of this prediction.

The stochastic nature of the Kriging prediction can also be seen as an indicator of the epistemic uncertainty affecting the prediction. In the context of process monitoring this information can be used in a very useful reliability metric \hat{R} corresponding to the "epistemic" probability that this sample is safe. Given the fact that failures correspond to negative values of performance this probability can be estimated as follows:

$$\hat{R}(X) = 1 - \Phi\left(\frac{-\hat{\mu}_K(X)}{\hat{\sigma}_K(X)}\right) \quad (1)$$

with Φ the standard normal cumulative distribution function.

The posterior STD also allowed the development of so-called adaptive Kriging approaches [11] [12] where a near-optimal DoE is iteratively built to minimize the modelling error. This strategy is very relevant for in-line monitoring since the process drift might push the process in areas of the input space for which the calibration of the surrogate is not satisfactory. To allow the surrogate model to automatically update its calibration in relevant areas two elements are proposed and discussed in section 3.4: a criterion to decide when refinement is necessary and a strategy to select which sample should be selected to enrich the DoE.

3.4 Digital-twin-assisted process control under uncertainty

The last two sections presented the two key elements of the proposed grey-box digital twin: respectively the model predicting the possible next states of process drift and allowing for a fast estimation of the associated performances. This section is dedicated to the development of an automated scheme taking advantage of both of these models and conducting process control while avoiding the occurrence of process failures.

Figure 6 gives an overview over the full process. The process is initiated by selecting an initial x_c based on an educated guess and building the initial Kriging model of the limit state function $g(x)$. In this first implementation, process control is performed over a set time period, given by T processes. As x_{uc} is unknown, it needs to be extrapolated for the n following time steps as described in chapter 3.2.

Before proceeding, it is necessary to determine whether or not the process is sufficiently reliable (over the next n instances) with the chosen value of x_c . The reliability of an input vector $X = (x_c, x_{uc})$ can be estimated using equation 1. Because x_{uc} can take any value within the interval $I[\hat{x}_{uc}^{t...t+n\Delta t}]$ a conservative approach is taken. The reliability index considered is the one corresponding to the worst case scenario over the interval of possible values for the non-controllable parameter \hat{R}_c and is defined as

$$\hat{R}_c = \min_{x_{uc} \in \hat{x}_{uc}^{t...t+n\Delta t}} \left(\hat{R}(y(x_{uc}, x_c) \in [ylim]) \right). \quad (2)$$

Figure 6: Flowchart of the process of process control

Figure 7: Reliability indicator for the worst case x_{uc} in the estimated interval for $t+$.

In order to verify the level of reliability this conservative value is simply compared to a user-defined threshold $R_{c,max}$:

$$\hat{R}_c > R_{c,max}. \quad (3)$$

This step prevents the algorithm to constantly fine-tuning the controllable parameter which would result in potential additional delays and multiplying the potential sources of error. Instead the controllable parameter is only adjusted when strictly necessary. If equation 3 holds and the current reliability is acceptable, the next n process steps can continue with the initial x_c . If not, the ideal $x_{c,opt}^{t+}$ has to be found given the worst case $\hat{x}_{uc,worst}^{t+}$ for each x_c . The optimization consist in finding the controllable parameter value that minimizes the worst case scenario reliability over the interval of possible controllable values and is given by

$$\hat{R}_{opt} = \max_{x_c \in I_c} \min_{x_{uc} \in \hat{I}_{uc}^{t+}} \left(\hat{R}(y(x_{uc}, x_c) \in [y_{lim}]) \right). \quad (4)$$

A visual representation of this equation and the optimisation process is given by figure 7 in the context of the application example discussed in section 4. The left-hand figure represents the input space of the problem (x_{uc}, x_c) and illustrates the prediction of the Kriging model with in blue (respectively red) the samples that are expected to be safe (respectively failing). The grey surface represents the interval of possible next x_{uc} values due to process-drift. On the right-hand figure the worst case reliability index is drawn on a matching x_c vertical axis. It can be observed how the reliability index decreases for extreme values of x_c since they are mostly associated with failure regions. It is also visible, that there is a safe area where the reliability index varies little. The optimisation does therefore not always have a unique result.

If the optimal reliability is higher than the critical reliability as selected by the operator

$$\hat{R}_{opt} > R_{crit}, \quad (5)$$

then the computed optimisation result $x_{c,id}$, which maximises the worst-case reliability, is a good choice as input variable for the next n time steps. In that case, no failure is expected for that parameter. It is advised, to choose the reliability threshold $R_{c,min}$ to refine x_c larger than the minimal permissible reliability R_{crit} . If equation 5 does not hold and the estimated reliability is smaller than the critical threshold, the process is estimated to fail within the next n time steps. This judgement can be due to a locally badly trained Kriging model which is checked by comparing the associated Kriging standard deviation to the previously defined threshold value σ_{lim} through

$$\sigma_{K,i} < \sigma_{lim}, \quad (6)$$

with $\sigma_{K,i}$ the standard deviation of the Kriging model at the point of interest $(x_{uc,worst}^{t+}, x_{c,opt}^{t+})$. If equation 6 holds true, the Kriging model is sufficiently exact and the process is halted. In that case, action is expected from the operator, such as changing the electrodes and consequently resetting (part of) the process drift. Otherwise the Kriging model is refined and the algorithm loops back to check for the need to adjust x_c . While there are different schemes and different learning functions can be employed to improve the accuracy of the Kriging model, it was decided to refine the model directly at the optimisation result $(x_{uc,worst}^{t+}, x_{c,opt}^{t+})$. This point was chosen as it ensures good precision around the area the process is expected to operate in during the next n time steps.

4 Example

In the example, the performance function y is analytically available. A well-known two-dimensional limit state function with four modes was chosen. It is given by

$$g(x_{uc}, x_c) = \min[g_1(x_{uc}, x_c), g_2(x_{uc}, x_c), g_3(x_{uc}, x_c), g_4(x_{uc}, x_c)] \quad (7)$$

Figure 8: Refinement of the Kriging meta model.

with

$$g_1(x_{uc}, x_c) = 3 + \frac{(x_{uc} - x_c)^2}{10} - \frac{x_{uc} - x_c}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$g_2(x_{uc}, x_c) = 3 + \frac{(x_{uc} - x_c)^2}{10} + \frac{x_{uc} - x_c}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$g_3(x_{uc}, x_c) = x_{uc} + x_c + \frac{7}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$g_4(x_{uc}, x_c) = -x_{uc} - x_c + \frac{7}{\sqrt{2}}.$$

The initial Kriging model is approximated by 10 Latin Hypercube samples, as shown in figure 8a. Process control is performed over a total of $T = 100$ processes with assuming that action can only be taken every $n = 4$ processes. The chosen function for x_{uc} can be seen in figure 5 and figure 9. Its extrapolation is based on virtual measurement data, which contain an additional noise term representing the measuring uncertainties. The minimal acceptable reliability of safety R_{crit} was set to 0.8 with $R_{c,max} = 0.9$ and $\sigma_{lim} = 0.12$.

Over the 100 processes, the Kriging model was refined five times. The refinement process and the evaluated samples can be seen in figure 8. After the fifth refinement, the limit state function is well estimated in the area of interest and it can be assumed, that further refinement steps will be rare for larger T .

Initially, only the centre points are well estimated by the Kriging model. Outside, the variance is relatively high. Therefore it is not surprising, that the Kriging model is refined as soon as the estimation of x_{uc} deviates from the well trained area. Figure 9 shows this behaviour well. It is also visible, that multiple samples in one area are necessary to refine the Kriging model with the necessary confidence.

The process control results are shown in figure 10. The numbering of the figure corresponds to the areas (a) to (e) marked in figure 9. The true x_{uc} of the processes is displayed together with the chosen x_c . The choice

Figure 9: Noise-free x_{uc} at each process, showing when the Kriging model was refined. The areas indicated by (a) - (e) correspond to the numbers of the subfigures in figure 8.

Figure 10: Optimised x_c and true x_{uc} for all optimised processes.

of x_c needs to be seen in relation to the Kriging estimation rather than the true limit state function, which is visible in the top subfigure. It can be seen, that the optimisation procedure, that is based on the Kriging estimation, yielded satisfying results. It is notable, that x_c is refined in intervals of four processes, which can be seen in figure 10 as well. In total the parameter x_c was adjusted 5 times, which is displayed in table 1.

Table 1: Value of x_c and the process it was adjusted.

Changed at process no.	$x_{c,ini}$	5	53	57	61	89
Value	0	-0.386	-0.276	-1.116	0.5881	0.700

While the processes 5 to 8 (figure 10a) and 57 to 60 (figure 10e) lie in the safe domain of the Kriging model, the reliability is not sufficient for these processes and possible failure was predicted. The reliability index is 0.570 and 0.706 respectively. That is due to the high variance of the Kriging model in these areas as well as due to the estimated interval of x_{uc}^{t+} .

In order to have good and reliable results, the estimation of the next x_{uc} is of utmost importance, as that is a leading factor in finding the optimal x_c . The estimated boundaries of x_{uc} for the next process can be seen in comparison to the true values in figure 11. While occasionally the boundaries are too small, they are well chosen in general and neither over- nor underestimate the true value of x_{uc} notably. It can be said that the extrapolation scheme worked well in this application.

Figure 11 shows, that the lower boundary for \hat{x}_{uc}^{5-8} is significantly lower than the true values. This is not surprising, as this was the first instance where process control was performed and the estimation of x_{uc} was based on only four monotonically decreasing samples. Overall, the estimation of x_{uc} is satisfying and the real behaviour was captured sufficiently. When the true limit state function is unknown, figure 11 gives a good indication on whether the reliability index can be trusted and if it is a sufficient measure of production results.

Figure 11: Estimation of the interval for x_{uc}^{t+} and true x_{uc} .

Figure 12 shows the estimated best x_c of at each process with respect to the true, noise-free x_{uc} and sets it in comparison with the true limit state function. It can be seen, that the adaptive refinement of x_c and of the Kriging model is working well and that in most cases the results are correctly estimated and in the safe domain. Out of the 96 processes that were included in the process control, only 2 lie in the failure domain. These two belong to process 55 and 56, for which the method computed a reliability of only 36 %. Their failure was therefore correctly predicted. Regardless, the optimisation was good given the Kriging model. Out of the 96 processes that control was applied to, 68 processes have an estimated reliability index above 99.99 % and 76 processes have an estimated reliability above 98 %.

Figure 12: Optimal input vs. true x_{uc}

5 Conclusion

In this paper, a methodology utilising a grey-box approach to perform near-real time process control for a simple application affected by process drift was presented. The developed methodology performed process control reliably and the combination of white-box and black-box model proved well suitable for such applications. The grey-box model provides a very good basis to build a more profound and complex model in the future. It is pointed out, that the ability to perform process control over a freely chosen number of time steps or process is of great interest also in different areas of application. It was possible to demonstrate the wide range of applicability of the method and its future potential.

The learning function to refine the Kriging model needs to be chosen application specific and has a large influence on the result quality. Thus developing a learning function that is specifically tailored to adaptive, process-oriented refinement, is an interesting topic to further look into in the future.

In future work, the methodology will be employed to a more complex example, also considering real data. In that case, a different extrapolation scheme to estimate x_{uc}^{t+} may be beneficial to utilise, such as Bayesian compressive sensing in combination with Karhunen-Loève expansion [17] or GP-NARX [18]. An easy to implement and very interesting adjustment, is to compute the reliability index for each process individually. This modification would make it possible to predict if only one process will fail but the results will stabilise themselves afterwards. That way a deeper insight into the process can be gained and the operator can take better informed decisions.

Furthermore, when the examples complexity and accuracy increases and additionally aleatory and epistemic uncertainties and actual measurement data are considered, multifidelity adaptive Kriging meta-modelling as well as methods for variance reduction such as control variates are beneficial to employ as well.

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